

(1) Overview

Title

SyncRecord - An Android application for creating ad-hoc microphone arrays from smartphones.

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Abstract

SyncRecord is an open-source Android application that enables the synchronisation of audio recordings across multiple, spatially distributed smartphones, transforming the grouped devices into an ad hoc, synchronised microphone array. The system employs an audible pseudo-random binary sequence (PRBS) signal emitted from the devices' speakers and cross-correlates the captured audio to extract propagation-delay information embedded in the audio streams. This approach reduces temporal misalignment across recordings to within $42 \mu\text{s}$ (2 samples at 48 kHz), and enables the estimation of the distance between any pair of devices to a mean accuracy of 14 mm. A key part of the system architecture is its server-side framework, which facilitates inter-device communication, real-time audio streaming, and signal processing. The server-side component can be deployed locally to minimise latency, enhance data privacy, and provide additional control over data handling. Alternatively, this component can operate via a cloud-based server when scalability or computational offloading is required. SyncRecord prioritises transient data handling, with cloud deployment having no audio stored beyond the recording session, and all existing streams removed, enhancing data privacy. The application and source code are publicly available via GitHub and CodeBerg, providing a foundation that can be adapted, extended, or integrated into existing audio capture workflows where source localisation, source separation, or other multi-channel audio processing could be beneficial.

Keywords

Synchronisation; Smartphones; Android; ad-hoc microphone array; PRBS; audio localisation; open-source

Introduction

Microphone (mic) arrays are central to a wide range of acoustic applications, including source localisation, beamforming, and speech enhancement [1, 2, 3, 4]. Conventional mic arrays depend on dedicated hardware and precise clock synchronisation, which limits scalability and increases cost [5, 6, 7]. Modern smartphones integrate high-quality microphones, speakers, and wireless communication interfaces, provide an opportunity for a low-cost and democratised alternative [8, 9]. The main challenges in transforming a group of smartphones into a distributed mic array are accurate device localisation and temporal synchronisation across devices.

Previous approaches to synchronisation have typically relied on external timing references, such as Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) or Network Time Protocol (NTP), or hardware-based synchronisation. These approaches, while accurate, require additional equipment and coordination, which might pose a challenge for ad hoc deployment [6, 7].

SyncRecord addresses these limitations by using an audible maximum length sequence (MLS) pseudo-random binary sequence (PRBS) signal, emitted and recorded by each device to achieve both temporal alignment and spatial localisation. The MLS is generated with an 8-bit Fibonacci linear-feedback shift register (LFSR) whose taps follow the primitive polynomial $x^8 + x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + 1$. This produces an MLS sequence of 255 bits. The duration of the sequence is increased using a bit-repeat factor ($\delta = 3$), which each bit is repeated three times, expanding the sequence to 765 bits. The sequence is then concatenated three times, yielding the final synchronisation bit sequence (SBS) of 2295 bits in length. The distance between each pair of devices in the array is measured via the propagation delay observed when a predefined SBS signal is emitted by one device and recorded the other. Owing to the autocorrelation properties of MLS PRBS signals, the cross-correlation of a pristine copy of the emitted audio and the received audio signal yields a distinct peak, the position of which indicates the propagation delay. By analysing each set of pairwise delays between devices, the system estimates both relative timing offsets and the Euclidean distances between nodes (each device being a node in the mic array), enabling simultaneous synchronisation and relative localisation using the captured audio. This exchange of SBS signals and resulting measurement of each recording device's position is carried out during a synchronisation protocol that takes place after each device has been placed in position and before synchronised multi-channel recording commences.

SyncRecord is implemented for Android devices that support access to unprocessed audio through `MediaRecorder.AudioSource.UNPROCESSED` [10, 11]. This ensures that the recorded signals are free from system-level modification, thereby preserving the integrity of the signal for precise delay estimation. The application consists of two components: a server and a client. The server, which can be deployed either locally or on a cloud platform, coordinates inter-device communication and manages the synchronisation workflow. The client application, installed on each smartphone, handles audio capture, playback of the audible SBS, and communication with the

server. When the server is cloud-deployed, all recorded data is transient and not stored persistently on the server, post-recording.

The open-source nature of the software facilitates modification and integration into existing research workflows, or in any impromptu audio capture situation in which synchronised multi-channel recording and processing could be of benefit.

The key contributions of this work are as follows:

- A software framework for distributed audio capture, comprising: an Android app, SyncRecord; a server-side NodeJS component to facilitate inter-device communication; and a set of audio signal processing routines implemented in Python.
- A novel method of temporal synchronisation between smartphones in a shared audio environment. In the SyncRecord system, this novel method is used to perform synchronisation between recording nodes in an ad hoc mic array. Under test conditions, the synchronisation was within $42 \mu\text{s}$, or 2 samples at a sampling frequency of 48 kHz.

This paper describes the software architecture, deployment options, and evaluation of SyncRecord.

Application features

The SyncRecord app is installed and runs on each device in the ad hoc mic array. It manages local recording, playback of the audio SBS, and real-time streaming of recorded audio to the back-end server. The server-side component, which can be deployed locally or on a cloud platform, coordinates inter-device communication and performs cross-correlation-based propagation delay estimation and audio stream temporal alignment. In addition to the primary mode of operation (synchronised recording), the system offers two additional modes of operation (localise array devices and unsynchronised recording). Assuming the system is operating in synchronised recording mode, its principal features are:

- **Mic array creation.** A designated master device initiates an ad hoc mic array by generating a unique session identifier (UID), displayed as a four-character alphanumeric code.
- **Add device to a mic array.** To add a new device to the array, the UID is typed in to the app on that device.
- **Coordinated start.** Using server-side signalling, the master device issues a “start record” command. Each participating device acknowledges receipt and begins recording simultaneously.
- **SBS emission protocol.** The master emits the predefined SBS signal, followed by each other participating device emitting the same SBS in a predefined order. This ensures that all devices transmit and record the entire sequence, providing the data necessary for propagation delay estimation.

- **Audio streaming.** The client app captures raw 16-bit pulse-code modulation (PCM) audio at a sampling rate of 48 kHz via the Android AudioRecord API. A dedicated recording thread continuously populates a memory buffer, a Base64-encoded snapshot of which is subsequently transmitted to the server via a network socket. Each buffer snapshot is encapsulated in a JSON object containing a cumulative byte-offset metadata field. The server-side logic uses these offsets to perform non-sequential file assembly. By writing incoming data to specific absolute positions within a file on disk, the system maintains signal integrity even if JSON objects arrive out of order due to network disturbances.
- **Server-side estimation of propagation delays and inter-device distances.** After all devices have emitted and captured the SBS sequence, the server performs cross-correlation between a stored reference SBS and each recorded audio stream. The resulting peaks are used to determine the inter-device distances, defining the relative geometry of the array.
- **Graceful termination.** Once all synchronisation emissions are complete, all devices continue recording and streaming audio data to the server. When the user presses “stop” on the master device, all devices are signalled to instruct them to stop recording. Each device signals the master to confirm that recording has stopped. Finally the master signals the server to begin post-processing.
- **Post-processing synchronisation.** Using the device-specific time offsets obtained during the earlier synchronisation protocol, the server aligns the recorded audio streams, producing synchronised multi-channel audio. For compatibility with most audio production environments, the multi-channel audio is stored as a set of single-channel audio files, each of which has been truncated at its start so that all recordings begin at the same time. In testing, a mean per-channel synchronisation error of 42 μ s was observed.
- **Data handling.** The data handling differs between cloud-hosted or locally-hosted server deployment.
 - Cloud-hosted server: After the recording session ends, the server generates a temporary download link for the master device. The master device downloads the compressed archive containing the multi-channel audio files and associated metadata. Once downloaded, the server deletes all data from that recording session.
 - Locally-hosted server: When the server runs on a local machine, no download link is created. The streamed audio files remain stored on that machine after the session finishes, allowing the user to access them directly from the server for further offline analysis or archiving. The files are not automatically removed.

On the first run of the SyncRecord client app, the user is required to give permission for the app to access the device microphone.

If the device does not support `MediaRecorder.AudioSource.UNPROCESSED` a notification is given to the user.

On the app home screen, two options are available. If the user chooses to create an array, a new mic array is initiated and that device is designated as the master device. If the user wants to join an existing array, they choose the Join Array option.

When a new mic array is initiated, the master device generates a four-character alphanumeric UID and displays it. The master is automatically assigned as device 1 and can select one of three options

- Synchronised recording.
- Localise array devices.
- Unsyncronised recording.

When a device joins an existing array using the array UID, it is assigned as a slave.

Each slave device is assigned a numerical identifier based on the order in which it joins the array.

The master device provides three operational modes for recording sessions:

- **Synchronised recording** (default mode): This mode combines the synchronisation protocol (described briefly above and in greater detail in the signal processing section below) with continued recording to create temporally synchronised audio streams from devices within the mic array. Devices record and stream audio to the server, first completing the synchronisation protocol mentioned above, then continue to record audio until the user presses the stop button on the master device. Two Python scripts, `Detection.py` and `SyncAudio.py`, run on the server during synchronised recording. `Detection.py` generates inter-device distance metadata, and `SyncAudio.py` realigns the audio streams based on the metadata, compresses all audio streams and metadata into a zipped archive. The parent server process then sends a download link to the master device.
- **Unsynchronised recording**: All devices capture and stream audio to the server. When the master terminates the session, the server compiles the recorded audio streams into a compressed archive and provides a link to the master device that allows downloading of the recording archive. No synchronisation of audio streams occurs.
- **Localise array devices**: In this mode, the synchronisation protocol takes place, but only to obtain the inter-device distance information. No continuous audio is recorded or stored after the synchronisation protocol is complete.

Practical considerations for ad-hoc deployment

When configuring a group of smartphones as an ad hoc mic array, the acoustic characteristics of each device influence overall performance. Because the built-in microphones are directional – their sensitivity varies with angle of incoming sound – SBS detection and accurate delay estimation are more reliable when each phone is kept within audible range of the other phones and is oriented so that its microphone points in the approximate direction of the centroid of the mic array.

Client-server communication

The client application, installed on each smartphone within the mic array, includes a default https socket configuration that connects to a public demonstration server at `https://syncrecord.eu:3000`. Users who wish to operate their own instance of the server – either hosted locally or deployed on a cloud platform – can reconfigure this setting within the app.

From the main screen, selecting the options button and then choosing *Socket Address* opens a configuration dialogue. Within this menu, the user specifies the server address and selects the connection type: Cloud or Local.

To configure the connection settings, the user selects *Socket Address* under the settings menu.

By default the client app connects to *https://syncrecord.eu* port *3000* on a cloud server.

In the menu, the user enters the server address and port, and selects if it is locally or cloud-hosted.

For cloud-based deployments, the connection uses an HTTPS domain and is authenticated through a valid certificate associated with that domain. To allow secure connections in locally-hosted deployments, a matching self-signed SSL certificate is included with the server and built into the client app. In principle, the user could substitute their own self-signed certificate, which would require rebuilding the app. However, in practice, for a mic array formed on a local area network, this is unlikely to be a concern.

This configuration option allows users to redirect the client app to their preferred server endpoint, supporting both cloud and local deployment.

Figure 1: Flow chart for the synchronised recording option of the *SyncRecord* app.

Figure 2: Flow chart for the unsynchronised recording and localise array devices options of the *SyncRecord* app.

Implementation and architecture

The SyncRecord system architecture consists of two primary components: a server-side application responsible for communication and signal processing, and a client-side native Android app used for audio SBS emission, audio capture, and user interaction. By running natively, the client-side app gains access to raw audio capture. Together, these components form an ad hoc multi-device synchronised recording platform.

Figure 3: Visualisation of the SBS-based propagation delay estimation. **(Top)** An illustration of an ad hoc mic array, with four smartphones deployed around and oriented towards the array centroid. Device D_1 is emitting the synchronisation bit sequence (SBS) which propagates to other devices in the array. **(Bottom)** Cross-correlation analysis of the captured audio streams. The distinct peaks represent the time-shifted arrival of the SBS at each receiving device. The labels l'_{s1m1} , l'_{s1m2} , l'_{s1m3} , and l'_{s1m4}

identify the local time of arrival of device D_1 's emission at devices D_1 , D_2 , D_3 , and D_4 respectively.

Server-side implementation:

The server runs a `Node.js` application that leverages `Socket.io` to handle real-time communication between devices within the deployed mic array. When an ad hoc array is initiated by a master device, the server creates a dedicated `Socket.io room` for participating devices, identified by a unique mic array ID. Client devices then join using the mic array ID. Each room has its own set of audio file buffers, one to store the audio stream from each recording device. All commands from the master device to the slave devices and acknowledgements from slave devices to the master are relayed through the server.

The signal processing pipeline is implemented as two Python scripts. The first script, `Detection.py`, takes as its input the set of audio files stored on the server and processes the audio segments that contain the SBS emissions recorded by each device. The script cross-correlates each captured stream with a reference SBS template, producing three distinct correlation peaks per device in every stream (because the SBS contains three repetitions of the MLS). Then, for each pair of devices, the discrete-time delay between corresponding correlation peaks is extracted. Using devices D_2 and D_3 as an example, the delays calculated are $l'_{s3m2} - l'_{s2m2}$ and $l'_{s3m3} - l'_{s2m3}$. Note that because devices transmit in numbered order, a lower numbered device always transmits before a higher numbered device. Hence, the delay calculated for the stream of the lower numbered device (D_2 in this case) includes the round-trip propagation time plus additional delays, but the delay calculated for the higher numbered device (D_3 in this case) includes only the additional delays and no propagation time. Hence, by subtracting the shorter delay from the longer delay, the round-trip propagation time can be obtained. All computed delays are stored in the recording session metadata.

Figure 4: Illustration of PRBS event detection and cross-correlation analysis across devices.

Subplot 1: Raw audio recording from Device D_1 , showing SBS emissions from all three devices. Sections corresponding to Device D_2 and Device D_3 events are amplified and highlighted with gray regions for visibility.

Subplot 2: Cross-correlation output for Device D_1 's recording, with the same amplified and gray-highlighted sections for Device D_2 and Device D_3 SBS events.

Subplot 3: Raw audio recording from Device D_2 , displaying SBS emissions from all three devices, with amplified and gray-highlighted sections for Device D_1 and Device D_3 events.

Subplot 4: Cross-correlation output for Device D_2 's recording, with amplified and gray-highlighted sections for Device D_1 and Device D_3 SBS events.

A second Python script, `SyncAudio.py`, is invoked at the end of the recording session. This script uses the inter-device propagation delays and SBS event timing metadata generated by `Detection.py` to perform two tasks: temporal alignment of the audio streams and the preparation of the final output archive. `SyncAudio.py` accesses the discrete-time round-trip propagation delays (e.g. $\Delta l_{1,2}$) determined by `Detection.py` for each pair of devices in the array. These delays represent the time offsets caused by the physical separation of the devices

and the propagation speed of sound in the environment. Using propagation delays, the script calculates the expected arrival times of the SBS events for each device. By comparing the measured correlation peak positions with the theoretically expected positions, `SyncAudio.py` determines the per-device discrete-time offset required to align all streams to a signal global timebase. The script applies the computed discrete-time offsets to each audio stream, either truncating or padding the beginning of the stream as needed. This adjustment means that all recordings start at the same time point, with a maximum observed synchronisation error of $42 \mu\text{s}$ (2 samples at 48 kHz). The end of each stream remains unaltered to preserve the integrity of the recorded audio.

Once the streams are aligned, `SyncAudio.py` then performs the following steps:

- The script bundles both the original (unsynchronised) and the synchronised audio streams into a structured directory.
- The script appends the synchronisation metadata to the archive.
- The final output – a compressed archive containing the audio files and metadata – is generated. If the server is cloud-hosted, it provides the master device with a temporary download link to retrieve the archive. For locally-hosted servers, the archive remains stored on the server for direct access by the user.

Figure 5: Temporal alignment of audio streams from multiple devices.

Top three subplots: Raw audio recordings from devices D_1 , D_2 and D_3 , respectively, displaying on their individual local timebases. The SBS emission events appear at different discrete-time indices due to the independent device clocks and recording start time, and variable propagation delays.

Bottom three subplots: The same audio streams after temporal alignment to a common global timebase. The determined discrete-time misalignments relative to device D_1 's SBS event are used to shift each stream accordingly to achieve synchronisation across audio streams.

Client-side implementation:

The SyncRecord Android app provides an interface for managing recording sessions, connecting to the server, and capturing raw audio. The app uses `MediaRecorder.AudioSource.UNPROCESSED` to ensure unprocessed audio capture, which is critical for accurate delay estimation and synchronisation. At launch, the app performs a compatibility check to verify support for unprocessed audio. If the device lacks this capability, the user is notified so that they are aware of possible inaccurate recordings.

Each ad hoc mic array session begins with the master device generating a unique session identifier (UID). This UID is shared with additional slave devices, which join the session using the provided alphanumeric code. Once the array is formed, the master device coordinates all subsequent actions – such as starting or stopping recording – via socket events relayed through the server.

Signal processing

The Android client app captures raw 16-bit Pulse-Code Modulation (PCM) audio at a sampling rate of 48 kHz via the `AudioRecord` API. A dedicated recording thread continuously writes incoming audio samples into a circular memory buffer. At each transmission window, the current state of the buffer is snapshotted and encoded as a Base64-encoded binary payload. This process ensures thread-safe data extraction, preventing buffer modification during transmission.

Each Base64-encoded audio chunk is encapsulated in a JSON packet, which includes a cumulative byte-offset field (referred to as the “total data” variable). This offset tracks the total number of bytes captured up to that point, enabling the server to position the incoming chunk at the correct absolute location within the reconstructed audio file. By writing data to these explicit offsets, the server reassembles a continuous audio timeline, even in the presence of out-of-order packet delivery or occasional loss. This approach minimizes latency and enhances robustness against network instability.

The raw audio captured by each device is temporarily saved as discrete-time 16-bit PCM samples, $m_D(n)$. During the SBS-emission synchronisation protocol, every recorded signal contains time-shifted, attenuated copies of all emitted SBS signals, together with background noise and ambient sounds.

Propagation delay estimation is performed by the Python script `Detection.py`, which extracts the segments of each recording containing the SBS emissions. These segments are used to measure round-trip propagation times, from which inter-device distances are derived. For each audio stream captured by the microphone array, the recorded signal is cross-correlated with a reference SBS template, producing the cross-correlation function $G_{Dp}(l)$:

$$G_{Dp}(l) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} m_D(n+l)p(n) \quad (1)$$

The discrete-time lags – $l'_{s_A m_A}$, $l'_{s_B m_A}$, $l'_{s_A m_B}$ and $l'_{s_B m_B}$ – represent the arrival times of each emitted SBS signal at each device, referenced to their local timebases. These lags appear as distinct peaks in the cross-correlation functions $G_{Ap}(l)$ and $G_{Bp}(l)$.

The indices of these peaks, denoted as L_{Dp} , are identified by locating the maxima of the correlation coefficients.

$$L_{Dp} = \arg \max_{l, N} G_{D,p}(l) \quad (2)$$

The audio SBS signal emitted by each device consists of the bit-repeated MLS that is repeated three times. Because of this, the cross-correlation function exhibits three distinct peaks per device. A single cross-correlation does not provide distance information on its own; however, by comparing the lag values of the peaks associated with each audio SBS event across a pair of recordings, the round-trip propagation delay between the devices can be extracted.

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the discrete time differences between the SBS arrival instants are:

$$\Delta l_{A(A,B)} = \left\| l'_{s_B m_A} - l'_{s_A m_A} \right\| \quad \Delta l_{B(A,B)} = \left\| l'_{s_B m_B} - l'_{s_A m_B} \right\| \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta \tau_{A(A,B)} = \Delta l_{A(A,B)} T_s \quad \Delta \tau_{B(A,B)} = \Delta l_{B(A,B)} T_s \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta l_{A,B} = \left\| \Delta l_{A(A,B)} - \Delta l_{B(A,B)} \right\| \quad (5)$$

Here, $\Delta l_{A(A,B)}$ represents the discrete-time offset between the paired SBS events, for device D_A and device D_B , as captured in the stream from device D_A , while T_s denotes the sampling period. The inter-device distance r_{AB} is derived from the difference between the two round-trip time estimates.

$$r_{A,B} = \left(\frac{\Delta \tau_{A(A,B)} - \Delta \tau_{B(A,B)}}{2} \right) c \quad (6)$$

Where c is the acoustic propagation speed. For typical indoor conditions, we use the average speed of sound in air, $c \approx 343$, m/s. These equations allow the system to convert measured local peak lags into accurate distance estimates between paired devices D_A and D_B .

Audio stream alignment

Using the estimated inter-device discrete-time round-trip propagation delay, $\Delta l_{A,B}$, the expected inter-device propagation delay for acoustic signals travelling between each pair of devices can be determined. The audio SBS emissions associated with a given pair of devices should therefore appear in the corresponding streams $\frac{\Delta l_{A,B}}{2}$ samples apart when referencing a global timebase.

$$l_{sAmB} = l_{sAmA} + \frac{\Delta l_{A,B}}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$l_{sAmA} = l'_{sAmA} \quad (8)$$

Where, l_{sAmB} is the theoretically expected position of the SBS emitted by device D_A received at device D_B , referencing the global timebase. And, l_{sAmA} is the same SBS emission event, but received at device D_A . Since the timebase of device D_A is used as the global timebase, then $l_{sAmA} = l'_{sAmA}$.

By comparing the measured correlation-peak positions with the theoretically expected positions derived from the synchronisation protocol, the system

computes a time offset for each stream. This offset is applied to shift the entire recording forward or backward, as required, aligning the SBS peaks to their expected positions across all channels. This is illustrated in Figure 5.

$$x_{A,B} = l_{sAmB} - l'_{sAmB} \quad (9)$$

Where, l_{sAmB} is the SBS emitted by device D_A being received at device D_B , on the global timebase (determined during the synchronisation protocol), and l'_{sAmB} is the SBS emitted by device D_A arriving at device D_B , on the local timebase of device D_B .

Let $m_D(n)$ denote the discrete-time audio signal for device D , where n is the sample index. The reference audio stream, $m_{D_1}(n)$ remains unchanged. For each additional audio stream, the alignment process adjusts the signal according to the mismatch value $x_{A,B}$.

If the stream $m_{D_B}(n)$ is advanced relative to the reference ($m_{D_A}(n)$), the beginning of the signal is trimmed to shift its onset backwards in time:

$$y_B(n) = m_{D_B}(n + x_{A,B}), \quad 0 \leq n < N_{D_B} - x_{A,B} \quad (10)$$

If the stream $m_{D_B}(n)$ is delayed relative to the reference, it is prepended with zeros to shift the offset later in time:

$$y_B(n) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq n < x_{A,B} \\ m_{D_B}(n - x_{A,B}), & x_{A,B} \leq n < N_{D_B} + x_{A,B} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The synchronised streams are stored, and the maximum length N_{max} is updated to ensure all streams are of sufficient length for further processing:

$$N_{max} = \max(N_{max}, \text{length}(m_D)) \quad (12)$$

The result is a set of temporally aligned audio streams, in which the underlying acoustic content is synchronised to within five samples. This alignment enables further downstream processing, such as source localisation or multi-channel analysis.

Quality control

A combination of manual end-to-end testing with unit testing and integration testing was employed to ensure functionality and stability. However, it is important to acknowledge that all testing was performed using multiple units of a single device model, the **OnePlus 6**. This device was chosen due to its confirmed support for *MediaRecorder.AudioSource.UNPROCESSED*, a critical requirement for unprocessed audio capture in the system.

- Unit testing:

Manual unit testing was performed on individual components and functions of the application throughout the development process. This ensured that each module operated correctly in isolation, adhering to its specified requirements.

- Integration testing:

Integration testing focused on verifying the interaction between different modules within the application. This step was crucial for confirming that the integrated system functioned as intended on the OnePlus 6, particularly in scenarios involving multiple devices.

- Manual end-to-end testing:

Manual end-to-end testing served as the primary validation method. This involved real-world usage scenarios using mic arrays made up of multiple OnePlus 6 devices, covering the entire workflow from device setup and connection to data acquisition and synchronisation. The goal was to ensure seamless operation and identify any potential issues in the user experience or system performance.

- Validation of system accuracy

Ground-truth distance measurement:

To validate the accuracy of the distance-estimation algorithm, smartphones running the Android app were arranged within a scene captured by a camera. Post-processing of the captured images provided the true Euclidean distances for every pair of phones. These measured distances served as a ground-truth reference, against which the SyncRecord system's estimated inter-device distances were compared. This comparison quantified the accuracy and reliability of the distance-estimation algorithm.

Audio-stream synchronisation verification:

For each recording session, the system's estimated discrete-time propagation delays for each device pair were used to temporally align the audio streams. The alignment was performed pair-wise for all device combinations and then inspected jointly to confirm the existence of a single global time reference across the network of audio streams. This cross-pair alignment testing ensured that the synchronisation protocol effectively aligned all audio streams.

(2) Availability

A public demonstration cloud-based server is available through <https://syncrecord.eu:3000> where a user can create a recording session and use the service immediately, in conjunction with the Android application available in the Github or CodeBerg repository, or software archive, listed in the software location section of this paper. All source code is available for use under the MIT license.

Operating system

The SyncRecord Android app runs on a wide selection of smartphones running Android 10 or later, provided that the device supports `MediaRecorder.AudioSource.UNPROCESSED`. This capability is essential for the application to capture the raw audio it requires. The experimental configuration employed for testing is described below.

Client Device

Model: OnePlus 6 (A6000 and A6003), running Android 11.

Server

- Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS

or

- Windows 11

Programming languages

- Python 3.10.12
- Node.js 12.22.9
- Kotlin 1.9.0

Additional system requirements

Client Device:

- Microphone
- Speaker
- Network connectivity

Dependencies

- Socket.io
- https
- express
- python-shell
- multer
- path
- numpy
- sys
- scipy

List of contributors

The list of authors includes all the contributors.

Software location:**Archive**

Name: SyncRecord

Persistent identifier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20383393>

Licence: MIT

Publisher: Zenodo

Version published: v1.0.0

Date published: 25/05/26

Code repository

Name: SyncRecord

Code repository on GitHub :

<https://github.com/PadraicMCE/SyncRecord>

Code repository on CodeBerg :

<https://codeberg.org/PMcEvoy/SyncRecord>

Persistent identifier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20383393>

Licence: MIT

Date published: 25/05/26

Language

The repository, documentation, and all text in the software are in English.

(3) Reuse potential

SyncRecord has reuse potential across various domains. The core functionalities of the application, including audio stream synchronisation, device distance determination, and relative location estimation, can be adapted and extended.

- Enhanced audio recording:

SyncRecord can be used to enhance audio recording in various scenarios. By utilising multiple smartphones as a synchronised microphone array, high-quality audio can be captured from various locations, potentially improving noise reduction and signal quality.

- Acoustic research and experimentation:

SyncRecord can be a valuable tool for acoustic research and experimentation. The ability to create and configure ad hoc, synchronised microphone arrays without dedicated hardware opens up possibilities for studies in sound source localisation and other acoustic analysis.

The reusability of SyncRecord is further enhanced by its open-source nature, allowing developers and researchers to modify and extend the application to suit their specific needs. SyncRecord has the potential to contribute beyond its initial scope.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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